

THEORETICAL DELIBERATIONS REGARDING TERMS AND TERMINOLOGY IN THE FIELD OF LINGUISTICS ARE BEING DISCUSSED

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ANNOTATION

Uzbek linguist P. Nishonov states: "a term is a word or a combination of words denoting the concept of a special field of knowledge or activity, a lexical unit that is limited by the scope of a special field in terms of semantics and expresses a concept related to this field" [6.17].

Key words: term, ambiguity, terminology, lexical unit, semiological system;

Indeed, the scientist's opinion is realized in connection with the emergence of this term within the framework of a special field. Of course, each term appears in a special context as an expression of the named object or behavior related to this field, and serves as a great help in naming this object.

In researches, when clarifying the concept of "term", criteria based on its four signs are listed:

- 1) term - a word or word combination consisting mainly of nouns;
- 2) the term clearly expresses a certain concept;
- 3) the term is mainly used within the field to which it belongs;
- 4) the term is not prone to ambiguity.

In many cases, we see that the term is mainly made up of nouns. They are made depending on the noun group. No matter how much we learn about the term, we must not forget that the term is a word that is studied within a field. The term is implemented depending on the characteristics of the object in question. The term refers to one subject and does not require a lot of meaning. In many cases, it is used in the same sense. Only in some cases, it can also depend on types.

According to the linguist scientist A. Mamadaliev: "A term is a lexical unit that requires precision (more precisely, a definition of the concept corresponding to the term)." The opinion of the scientist is also reflected in the definition of V. P. Danilenko: "under the concept of a term we understand the naming of a special concept and a word, a phrase in the field of special use that requires a definition"[5.89].

The contribution of Uzbek scientists to the development of the field of terminology and their opinions in this regard are incomparable. In particular, S. Usmanov contributed a lot of information for the development of the field of terminology, all of which are important. Terminological units: "... any innovations both in the field of production tools and in the field of culture and science are first expressed through language units, or rather, terms. In this sense, terminology (a set of terms in a certain language) is a witness, a mirror of modern history" [5.89]. We somewhat agree with the valuable opinions of the scientist, but we need to enrich this definition in order to express the terms. In our opinion, the terms that have arisen in any special field are certainly the needs of this profession or reality, although the terms are primarily used in the form of neologisms in the structure of speech and language units, but not all of them are represented by a new name. In addition, depending on the development of the field, they will take a place in the general vocabulary.

The terminology of any science is not just a list of terms, but a semiological system that names a system of concepts that reflects a certain scientific outlook. When the need for a term system is felt, at this time the science has reached a sufficiently high level of development. In other words, the development of the concept at this level and the giving of a specific scientific name is characterized by the emergence of terms.

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